

VUCA Transformational Leadership Towards Indonesian Micro and SMEs: Mediating Role of Organizational Learning and Dynamic Capabilities

Robi Mantik Tarliman¹, John Tampil Purba², Niko Sudibjo³, Yohana F. C. P. Meilani⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Universitas Pelita Harapan, Indonesia

Email: robi.tarliman@gmail.com

Abstract

In the era of Industry 4.0 + 5 G with VUCA world conditions, it is a period of radical uncertainty. VUCA describes something full of vagueness, directionless, very rapidly changing situations that come from unclear cause and effect, which is very ironic. The purpose of this research is to find out transformational leadership with VUCA principles towards Micro and Indonesian SMEs through the role of organizational learning mediation and dynamic capabilities. Data collection technique using questionnaires with respondents as many as 472 MSME leaders in Jakarta. This type of research is quantitative with data analysis using *Structural Equation Modelling* (SEM). Based on the results of the analysis obtained the model equation $Y = 0.06X1 + 0.36X2$. The results of determinant coefficient (R²) testing showed a determinant coefficient of 0.43 meaning that 43% of organizational learning mediation variables and dynamic capabilities can explain transformational leadership taking into account vuca principles. While the remaining 57% were influenced by other variables outside of this study variable. Although MSMEs to achieve ideal conditions are very difficult but still need to strive for achievement through transformational leadership by creating dynamic learning organizations and capabilities.

Keywords: Leadership, Organizational Learning, Dynamic Capabilities.

INTRODUCTION

The development of information and communication technology led to the integration of large-scale internet-powered communications such as Robotics, Automobiles, and Augmented Reality impacting the changes that created new markets and new value networks of the Industrial Era 4.0 & 5G. In the era of Industry 4.0 + 5 G with VUCA world conditions, it is a period of radical uncertainty. VUCA is an acronym for *Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, and Ambiguity*. VUCA describes something full of vagueness, directionless, very rapidly changing situations that come from unclear cause and effect, which is very ironic.

The contribution of Human Resources to the VUCA era is indispensable, where effective leadership styles play an important role. Leadership style selection plays the most important role for all organizations, particularly in micro, small and medium enterprises. The number of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) continued to rise during the COVID-19 Pandemic in DKI Jakarta. Many new entrepreneurs are emerging in the capital region. Head of the Jakarta Provincial Government's Economic and Financial Bureau Mochamad Abbas said, as of Friday, December 24, 2021, the number of MSMEs in Jakarta had reached 289,370 (Halim & Rachman, 2021).

MSMEs to survive and thrive in this VUCA situation, must adapt and adopt to transform their business models to be relevant to the current situation (Deloitte, 2020). In developing a conceptual model of leadership style towards MSMEs with principles that take Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, Ambiguity, and Paradox into consideration, to create valuable and positive change in followers with the ultimate goal of developing followers into leaders. Organizations must confront the vuca world situation, based on the relevant leadership currently proposing to build VUCA Transformational Leadership (Johansen, 2009).

Leaders are challenged to find new approaches to leading their organizations and achieving sustainable success in new and diverse environments (VUCA). But leaders in the face of this uncertain environment get the demands to face current conditions such as opportunities and difficulties for leaders. Organizations must transform their capabilities through innovation and develop dynamic capabilities (Racela, 2014). Dynamic capability is a company's ability to systematically handle problems by identifying opportunities and making timely market-oriented decisions (Barreto, 2010). Dynamic capabilities are significantly influenced by leadership (Schoemaker et al., 2018a).

Rosing (2011) analyzed 11 leadership styles from 77 research journals the most powerful type of leadership related to innovation is Transformational Leadership. Leaders will need a long-term perspective and the capacity to design detailed plans to address the complexities of navigating change and mitigate the risks associated with vuca's impact. They should also be able to learn at work while practicing proven leadership skills. The process and level of organizational learning to

describe how strategic leaders influence every element of a learning system. Researchers implicitly assume a transformational leadership approach to organizational learning (Vera & Crossan, 2004).

The main stages of the individual learning process can be transferred to organizational learning, but the dynamics of organizational learning are more complex than individuals. This metaphor opens up new opportunities to understand the relationship between organization and knowledge, and between organizational action and organizational thinking. As Gherardi & Nicolini (2003) emphasize, "Organizational learning is a metaphor that encompasses two concepts, learning and organization, and allows exploration of an organization as if it were a subject that learns, processes information, reflects experience, and has knowledge, skills, and expertise", leadership construction and organizational learning processes at different levels of analysis. The mediation effect of an organizational context is integrated using models and propositions that describe the role of leaders with regard to new and existing learning (Berson, et al., 2006).

Based on the problems that occur in the current uncertain conditions, the right leadership style is needed to deal with these problems. Therefore, this research is to find out transformational leadership with VUCA principles towards Micro and Indonesian SMEs through the role of organizational learning mediation and dynamic capabilities.

THEORETICAL STUDIES

Organizational Learning

The main stages of the individual learning process can be transferred to organizational learning, but the dynamics of organizational learning are more complex than individuals. This metaphor opens up new opportunities to understand the relationship between organization and knowledge, and between organizational action and organizational thinking. As Gherardi & Nicolini (2003, p.47) emphasize, "Organizational learning is a metaphor that encompasses two concepts, learning and organization, and allows exploration of an organization as if it were a subject that learns, processes information, reflects experience, and has knowledge, skills, and expertise", leadership construction and organizational learning processes at different levels of analysis. The mediation effect of an organizational context is integrated using models and propositions that describe the role of leaders with regard to new and existing learning (Berson et al., 2006).

Dynamic Capabilities

Dynamic ability is an organizational ability that allows regular abilities to be changed over time. Erosion, substitution, and learning about high-level abilities through time are three problems facing dynamic ability (Collis, 1994). According to Teece et al., (1997), a company's ability to integrate, develop, and reconfigure internal and external competencies to deal with rapidly changing circumstances is referred to as dynamic capability. In line with Barreto (2010), a company's ability to systematically handle problems by identifying opportunities and making timely market-oriented decisions is referred to as dynamic capability.

Examples of dynamic capabilities such as conveying that product creation, strategic decision making, and alliance (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000). They claim that these competencies can be identified and that core procedures and activities can be compared across companies, but not across industries. Note that dynamic capability refers to a company's ability to build, expand, or customize its resources based on purpose (Helfat et al., 2007). The majority of literature reviews on the nature of such dynamic abilities (Breznik & hisrich, 2014) treats (Teece et al., 1997) are the same as the original definition of dynamic ability. Given the findings by studying procedures that are difficult to copy, dynamic capabilities seek to match business possibilities and user needs (Teece, 2014). Dynamic capabilities can be operationalized as the capacity (1) to perceive and shape opportunities and threats, (2) to capture opportunities, and (3) to maintain competitiveness by enhancing, combining, protecting, and, where necessary, reconfiguring the resources of business enterprises (Teece, 2007).

METHODS

This type of research is survey research with a quantitative approach. The sample in this study was 472 MSME leaders from 289,370 MSMEs in Jakarta Province. Data collection technique uses questionnaires with a scale of Likert 5 alternative answer options and is analyzed using *Structural Equation Modelling* (SEM). The instrument is tested for construct validity and reliability. The validity of a contract is the validity that shows the history of the test results are able to reveal a *trait* or a theoretical contract that he wants to measure, proving the validity of the contract is a process that continues in line with the development of the measured concept. The validity of the contract used in this study uses factor analysis that serves to summarize or reduce observational variables into new dimensional forms that present the main variables (factors).

Proving the validity of the contract used is 1) *exploratory factor analysis* which aims to investigate the factors contained in the observation points. Analysis of exploratory factors through *extraction* and *rotation* methods. In factor analysis used *principal components extraction* which aims to find out *the factor loading of each item* and *varimax rotation* aims to clarify the items that go into the factor. The results of the exploratory factor analysis continued using the analysis of confirmatory factors. 2) *confirmatory factor analysis* with the aim of affirming a theory of measurement in order to compare theoretical with empirical results.

After getting a valid instrument then estimate reliability. Reliability is a coefficient that shows the consistency level of measurement results of a test using the same measuring instrument for different people or at different times but the same conditions. Reliability instruments use *the Alpha Cronbach* formula with the help of SPSS 20.0 software and construct reliability that uses *the Construct Reliability (CR)* formula. The amount of reliability index is at least 0.70 this is because the greater the reliability index, the smaller the measurement error (Mardapi, 2012; Inscription and Istiyono, 2018).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Normality Test

Normality testing on Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) data analysis is required, meaning that the distribution of data used requires normal assumptions. The assumption of normality is met if it has a statistical value of z skewness and kurtosis greater than 0.05 or 5%. The results of the univariate normality test in this analysis are presented in.

Table 2. Test of Univariate Normality for Continuous Variables

Variable	Skewness		Kurtosis		Skewness and Kurtosis	
	Z-Score	P-Value	Z-Score	P-Value	Chi-Square	P-Value
DC1	-8.641	0.000	3.213	0.001	84.942	0.000
DC2	-7.382	0.000	-0.668	0.504	54.934	0.000
DC3	-10.018	0.000	4.769	0.000	123.096	0.000
DC4	-1.486	0.137	-0.234	0.815	2.263	0.323
DC5	-10.859	0.000	4.962	0.000	142.547	0.000
DC6	-10.741	0.000	4.828	0.000	138.671	0.000
OL1	-0.041	0.947	-12.957	0.000	167.891	0.000
OL2	5.740	0.000	-4.630	0.000	54.386	0.000
OL3	-0,019	0.985	-3.730	0.000	13.713	0.001
OL4	-5.151	0.000	4.247	0.000	44.581	0.000
OL5	6.120	0.000	-5.301	0.000	65.554	0.000
OL6	-1.118	0.263	-0.655	0.513	1.680	0.432
OL7	-6.136	0.000	4.247	0.000	55.679	0.000
VLT1	-6.831	0.000	3.203	0.001	56.923	0.000
VLT2	-2.159	0.031	-3.891	0.000	19.806	0.000
VLT3	-7.649	0.000	4.218	0.000	76.306	0.000
VLT4	-2.110	0.035	-3.842	0.000	19.209	0.000
VLT5	-6.855	0.000	2.703	0.007	54.300	0.000

Table 3. Test of multivariate Normality for Continuous Variables

Skewness		Kurtosis		Skewness and Kurtosis	
Value	Z-Score	P-Value	Value	Z-Score	P-Value
783.941	199.273	0.000	1375.233	42.367	0.000
				41504.655	0.000

It can be concluded that the data used does not meet the normal univariate or multivariate assumptions. Furthermore, because the data is not normal, in this study uses an alternative *normal score* to convert the data to normal.

Testing validity and reliability

The criteria in the EFA analysis must be met as follows *keyser Mayer Oikin (KMO)* value greater than 0.5; and significant value of *Barlett's Test of Sphericity* less than 0.05 (Ghozali, 2005). In addition, the *eigenvalue* value in *Total Variances Explained* is greater than 1.0 and the coefficient in *the Rotated Component Matrix* is greater than 0.40 (Azwar, 2015).

Table 4. Exploratory Factor Analysis 1

Number of Items	KMO Value	Sig Barlett's Test
18	0.815	0.000

Table 3, showing a KMO value of 0.815 and a significance value of *Barlett's test* of 0.000. These results showed that the KMO value > 0.5 and *Barlett's test value* < 0.05, it was concluded that the sample size used in this factor analysis was sufficient so that the EFA analysis could proceed to the next. Next to see how many components are formed from the 18 items of the statement can be seen from the total initial value of *eigen values* > 1.0 shown in Table 4.

Table 5. Total Initial Eigenvalues

Component	Initial Eigenvalues		
	Total	Variance (%)	Cumulative (%)
1	6.371	35.396	35.396
2	4.285	23.804	59.200
3	2.148	11.934	71.134

Summary Table 4, showing that *the total initial eigen values* > 1.0. Thus, it was concluded that there are 3 components formed from 18 items on the instrument with a described variance of 71,134%. Thus, it can be concluded that all items can be further analyzed through factor analysis by *extraction* and *rotation* method using varimax and obtained results as in Table 5.

Table 6. Rotated Component Matrix

	Component		
	1	2	3
DC1	,058	,865	,032
DC2	,066	,848	-,010
DC3	,041	,859	,043
DC4	,078	,758	,039
DC5	-,021	,909	,059
DC6	-,022	,901	,064
OL1	,704	,055	,305
OL2	,791	-,010	,254
OL3	,871	,045	,071
OL4	,792	,044	,198
OL5	,814	-,002	,253
OL6	,879	,058	,089
OL7	,767	,053	,183
VLT1	,370	,021	,737
VLT2	,169	,034	,884
VLT3	,196	,085	,752
VLT4	,164	,032	,890
VLT5	,202	,035	,736

So, continued at CFA, which is based on exploratory analysis that obtained 3 components and supported by the existence of theory then further analyzed using confirmation analysis. Structural Equation Modelling analysis results, as follows:

Figure 1. Standardized Solution

Figure 2. T value Solution

The latent variables are analyzed using SEM to determine valid and reliable indicator codes. Because good data is the result of a valid and reliable instrument. Here are the details of each variable.

Table 7. Results of Validity and Reliability Analysis

Latent Vaibel	Indicator Code	SLF \geq 0.50	T value $>$ 1.96	Ket	CR \geq 0.70	VE \geq 0.50	Ket
VLT (Y1)	VLT1	0.67	-	Valid	0,76	0,64	Reliable
	VLT2	0.99	20.69	Valid			
	VLT3	0.59	11.07	Valid			
	VLT4	0.99	20.72	Valid			
	VLT5	0.52	11.64	Valid			
DC (X1)	DC1	0.72	19.34	Valid	0,89	0,74	Reliable
	DC2	0.71	19.03	Valid			
	DC3	0.72	19.59	Valid			

Latent Variabel	Indicator Code	SLF ≥ 0.50	T value > 1.96	Ket	CR ≥ 0.70	VE ≥ 0.50	Ket
	DC4	0.60	15.57	Valid			
	DC5	0.99	32.22	Valid			
	DC6	0,98	31.81	Valid			
OL (X2)	OL1	0.64	16.68	Valid	0,71	0,61	Reliable
	OL2	0.98	31.77	Valid			
	OL3	0.64	16.60	Valid			
	OL4	0.58	14.75	Valid			
	OL5	0.99	32.63	Valid			
	OL6	0.64	16.92	Valid			
	OL7	0.52	13.01	Valid			

Based on table 6, it is obtained that there are 18 indicators with 3 latent variables and each indicator has passed the validity test so it can be said that respondents' answers to questions used to measure each construct or indicator are consistent and reliable / reliable.

Measurement Model Match Test

After the model is valid and reliable then next do a model match test. Hendryadi & Suryani (2014) states that the criteria in the CFA analysis can determine the suitability of the model with the help of using Lisrel 8.54 can be determined as follows: 1) chi-squared with a p-value of > 0.05; 2) *Root Mean Square Error of Approximation* (RMSEA) value ≤ 0.08. RMSEA is a value that attempts to correct the statistical tendency of chi-squared rejecting the model; 3) *The Goodness of Fit Index* (GFI) value ≥ 0.90 means the model tested has a good fit. GFI is an index that describes the overall suitability rate of the predicted model versus actual data; 4) *T-value* ≥ 1.96; 5) *Standardized loading factor* > 0.5.

Table 8. Model Match Test Results

GOF	Acceptable match rate	Model Index	Ket
Chi-Square	The smaller the better. (p-value ≥ 0.05)	143,09 (p value 0. 240)	Good fit
GFI	GFA ≥ 0.90 good fit 0.80 ≤ GFI ≤ 0.90 marginal fit	0.92	Good fit
RMSR	RMSR ≤ 0.05 good fit	0.035	Good fit
RMSEA	RMSEA ≤ 0.08	0.055	Good fit
CFI	CFI ≥ 0.90 good fit	0.92	Good fit

Based on Hooper et al (2008), assess the size of the model match by looking at the values of chi-square test, RMSEA, CFI and RMSR. Therefore, the match test shows the fit model, it can be concluded that the model used in this study can be used as a basis for analysis of the problems of this study.

Table 9. Results of structural equation analysis

Exogenous latent variables	Standardized coefficient	T value	Ket	R ²
X1	0.06	3,64	Significant	0.43
X2	0.36	7.94	Significant	

So that the structural equations model is $Y = 0.06X1 + 0.36X2$, the effect of each variable is independent of the dependent variable. In addition, you can see the coefficient of determinance (R²) which serves to show how much contribution is given simultaneously to dependent variables. This means that a determinant coefficient of 0.43 means that 43% of organizational learning mediation variables and dynamic capabilities can explain transformational leadership taking into account vuca principles. While the remaining 57% were influenced by other variables outside of this study variable.

Changing economic environments will redefine the business game and will also bring elements of volatility, uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity (VUCA) to an MSMEs. Although the scale of the business targeted by Small and Medium Micro Enterprises business is not as big as snapper class companies, many people are comfortable doing business at this level. Because of the advantages offered to micro and small and medium enterprises and these advantages are difficult to obtain at the giant business level. One of the main advantages is the ease of adopting innovation in business, especially in the field of technology.

The adoption of the latest technology becomes easier to do to increase the growth of MSME business because it does not have a convoluted bureaucracy and complicated systems. In addition to the ease of application of technology, excellence

in employee relationship factors due to its smaller scope, and flexibility to adapt the business to dynamic market conditions. This large-scale technological transformation will require different approaches to leadership.

Leaders are challenged to find new approaches to leading their organizations and achieving sustainable success in new and diverse environments (VUCA). But leaders in the face of this uncertain environment get the demands to face current conditions such as opportunities and difficulties for leaders. Organizations must change their capabilities through developing dynamic capabilities (Racela, 2014). Dynamic capability is a company's ability to systematically handle problems by identifying opportunities and making timely market-oriented decisions (Barreto, 2010). Dynamic capabilities are significantly influenced by leadership (Schoemaker et al., 2018a). Organizations must confront the vucap world situation, based on the relevant leadership currently proposing to build VUCA Transformational Leadership (Johansen, 2009).

In addition, the processes and levels of organizational learning describe how strategic leaders influence every element of the learning system. Researchers implicitly assume a transformational leadership approach to organizational learning (Vera and Crossan, 2004). The main stages of the individual learning process can be transferred to organizational learning, but the dynamics of organizational learning are more complex than individuals. This metaphor opens up new opportunities to understand the relationship between organization and knowledge, and between organizational action and organizational thinking. As Gherardi and Nicolini (2003, p.47) emphasize, "Organizational learning is a metaphor that encompasses two concepts, learning and organization, and allows exploration of an organization as if it were a subject that learns, processes information, reflects experience, and has knowledge, skills, and expertise", leadership construction and organizational learning processes at different levels of analysis. The mediation effect of an organizational context is integrated using models and propositions that describe the role of leaders with regard to new and existing learning (Berson, et al, 2006). Although achieving these ideal conditions is very difficult but still needs to be strived for achievement through transformational leadership and creating a learning organization. Finally, the growth rate, effective revolution resolution and organizational change performance depend on fundamentals such as capable transformational leadership, accurate strategies, the application of learning organizations within organizations (Ambarwati, 2003).

CONCLUSION

Organizations today are faced with the crucial question that must receive special attention: what must be done to succeed in global competition. Global competition will set aside any organization that does not have the right strategy in anticipation of change. So that every organization must plan the process of change or innovation through the establishment of a more challenging vision and the management of change more clearly and precisely so that it can overcome existing change barriers. MSMEs must face vucap's world situation, based on the relevant leadership currently proposing to build VUCA Transformational Leadership. Although achieving these ideal conditions is very difficult but still needs to be strived for achievement through transformational leadership and creating a learning organization. Finally, the growth rate, effective revolution resolution and organizational change performance depend on fundamentals such as capable transformational leadership, precise strategies, the application of learning organizations within organizations. Dynamic capability is a company's ability to systematically handle problems by identifying opportunities and making timely market-oriented decisions. Dynamic capabilities are significantly influenced by leadership.

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